

in the concentration range 2.0×10^{-5} to 2.0×10^{-4} mol dm^{-3} keeping all other conditions constant, did not show any significant effect on the rate of reaction.

Effect of varying acidity :

The effect of acid on the reaction was studied by using perchloric acid at constant concentrations of DL-methionine and cerium(IV) and keeping a constant ionic strength of 1.0 mol dm^{-3} at 31°. A constant amount of sulfuric acid coming from stock solution of cerium(IV) was also present in all cases. The rate constants increased with increase in [acid] (Table 1). The *in situ* $[\text{H}^+]$ concentration in the sulfuric acid-sulfate media was calculated using the known ionization constant⁶ of acid sulfate as in an earlier study⁷. The order in $[\text{H}^+]$ was fractional as found from a plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $\log [\text{H}^+]$. Cerium(IV) is known to form several complexes in acid sulfate media, such as $\text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}$, CeSO_4^{2+} , $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$, $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{HSO}_4^-)$ and $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$ as shown in equilibria (2)–(6),

Since the total cerium(IV) is distributed between different species with the equilibrium constants, K_{OH} , $\beta_1 (K_1)$, $\beta_2 (K_1 K_2)$, $\beta_3 (K_1 K_2 K_3)$ and $\beta_4 (K_1 K_2 K_3 K_4)$ characterizing such equilibria, the approximate concentration of such species may be calculated using eqn. (7) from the concentration of the dissolved [cerium(IV)] and acid sulfate, as also the competing equilibria and their constants,

$$[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{f}} \left\{ 1 + \frac{K_{\text{OH}}}{[\text{H}^+]} + \beta_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}] + \beta_2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 + \beta_3 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-] + \beta_4 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2 [\text{H}^+] \right\} \quad (7)$$

The results of such calculations are given in Table 2.

Effect of ionic strength and solvent polarity :

The effect of ionic strength was studied by varying the sodium perchlorate concentration in the reaction medium in the range 0.5 – 1.25 mol dm^{-3} and no significant effect on rate constant was observed.

The relative permittivity (*D*) effect was studied by varying the acetic acid-water content in the reaction mixture with all other conditions being maintained constant. Attempts to measure the relative permittivities were not successful. However, they were computed from the values of pure liquids⁸. No reaction of the solvent with the oxidant occurred under the experimental conditions. The rate constant, K_{obs} decreased with increase in acetic acid concentration. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ was linear with negative slope.

Polymerization study :

The reaction mixture containing acrylonitrile was kept for 4 h in an inert atmosphere. On diluting the reaction mixture with methanol, precipitate was obtained, which indicated the presence of free radical intervention in the reaction.

Effect of temperature :

The rate constants, *k* of the slow step of Scheme 1 were obtained from the intercept of the plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{DL-methionine}]$ at different temperatures and used to calculate the activation parameters. The values of *k* (s^{-1}) were 0.018, 0.021 and 0.026 at 31, 35 and 40°, respectively. The corresponding activation parameters were E_a , 27.3 ± 1.5 kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔH^\ddagger , 24.7 ± 1.3 kJ mol^{-1} ; ΔS^\ddagger , -196 ± 10 J K^{-1} mol^{-1} ; ΔG^\ddagger , 85.5 ± 4.0 kJ mol^{-1} .

Table 2. Variation of different Ce^{IV} species with $[\text{H}^+]$ on oxidation of DL-methionine by Ce^{IV} in acid medium*

Temp = 31°, $[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4}$, $[\text{DL-meth}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$, $I = 1.0$ mol dm^{-3}										
$[\text{HClO}_4]^a$	$[\text{H}^+]$	$[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$	$[\text{HSO}_4^-]$	α_0	α_1	α_2	α_3	α_4	α_5	$k_{\text{obs}} (\text{s}^{-1})$
		10^3	10^3	10^6	10^4	10^6	10^9	10^{11}	10^{14}	10^3
0.05	0.066	6.41	3.58	0.87	1.97	2.14	6.02	1.30	0.61	6.97
0.1	0.114	4.64	5.35	1.49	1.95	2.65	5.86	1.72	2.11	10.50
0.2	0.213	3.45	6.54	2.75	1.93	3.65	5.55	2.18	6.08	15.15
0.4	0.412	2.43	7.57	5.22	1.91	4.60	5.09	2.31	14.4	21.90
0.5	0.510	0.96	9.04	6.44	1.88	4.81	4.02	1.95	16.2	25.35

* $\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4$ and α_5 are the fraction of the total Ce^{IV} species, $\text{Ce}_p, \text{Ce}(\text{OH})^{3+}, \text{CeSO}_4^{2+}, \text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2, \text{HCe}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-,$ and $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$ respectively; all concentrations are in mol dm^{-3} .

^a A constant amount of H_2SO_4 coming from original stock solution of Ce^{IV} , i.e. 1×10^{-2} mol dm^{-3} is also present in all cases.

Mechanism :

The reaction between DL-methionine and cerium(IV) in acidic medium has a stoichiometry of 1 : 2 with less than unit order dependence on both perchloric acid and DL-methionine concentrations and a first order dependence on [Ce^{IV}]. No effect of the product was observed. The results suggest that cerium(IV) reacts with the substrate, DL-methionine, to give a complex (C) in an equilibrium step. This complex decomposes in a slow step to give a free radical derived from decarboxylated DL-methionine, which further reacts with another molecule of cerium(IV) in a fast step to yield the products (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The spectral evidence for the complex formation between oxidant and substrate was obtained by the UV-vis spectra of the oxidant and a mixture of substrate and oxidant. A bathochromic shift of about 5 nm, from 295 to 300 nm was observed. This result was also evident from the Michaelis-Menten plot and such complex formation between a substrate and oxidant was also observed in other studies⁹. The observed modest enthalpy of activation and a relatively low value of the entropy of activation and the higher rate constant of the slow step of the mechanism indicate that the oxidation presumably occurs by an inner-sphere mechanism. This conclusion is supported by the earlier work¹⁰. Since Scheme 1 is in accordance with the generally well accepted principle of non-complementary oxidations taking place in a sequence of one-electron steps, the reaction would afford a radical intermediate. A free radical scavenging experiment revealed such a possibility. This type of radical intermediate has also been observed in earlier work¹¹ on the acidic Ce^{IV} oxidation of various organic substrates.

Scheme 1 leads to the rate law of eqn. (8),

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}][\text{DL-Methionine}]}{1 + K[\text{DL-Methionine}]} \quad (8)$$

The term, $1 + K[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]$ in eqn. (8) approximates to unity in

view of the low concentration of Ce^{IV} used and the observed first order kinetics in [Ce^{IV}],

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]} = k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{kK[\text{DL-Methionine}]}{1 + K[\text{DL-Methionine}]} \quad (9)$$

Eqn. (9) can be rearranged to the following form which is used for the verification of the rate law,

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{kK[\text{DL-Methionine}]} + \frac{1}{k} \quad (10)$$

According to eqn. (10), the plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/[\text{DL-methionine}]$ should be linear and which was found to be so. The slope and intercept of such plot lead to the values of k and K at 31° of $18.8 \pm 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $6.6 \pm 0.3 \times 10^2 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$, respectively. Using these values, rate constants under different experimental data were calculated. There is a reasonable agreement between them (Table 1).

The active species involved in the mechanism can be understood as follows. The variation of rate with acidity was shown, in the results section, to parallel the trend of variation of concentration of the $\text{H}_3\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_4^-$ species with the acidity (Table 2). The mechanism (Scheme 1), will, therefore, involve the above species as shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2

The effect of ionic strength on the rate qualitatively explains the reaction between a charged species and a neutral species as given in Scheme 1. The effect of solvent on the reaction kinetics has been described in detail in the literature¹². For the limiting case of zero angle approach between two dipoles or an ion-dipole system, it has been shown¹³ that a plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ gives a straight line with a negative slope for a reaction between a negative ion and a dipole or two dipoles, and with a positive slope for a positive ion and dipole interaction. It has been observed that the plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ vs $1/D$ is a straight line with a negative slope, which

agrees with the proposed Scheme 2.

The moderate value of ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger were both favorable for electron transfer processes. The negative value of ΔS^\ddagger within the range of radical reactions has been ascribed¹⁴ to the nature of electron pairing and electron unpairing processes, and the loss of a degree of freedom, formerly available to the reactions on the formation of a rigid transition state. A negative value of ΔS^\ddagger suggests that the complex is more ordered than the reactants.

The rate law for the reaction can be derived from Scheme 2 as given below :

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k K_1 K_2 [\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}]_{\text{T}} [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{Methio}]}{1 + K_1 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2 [\text{H}^+] + K_1 K_2 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]^2 [\text{HSO}_4^-]^2 [\text{H}^+] [\text{Methio}]}$$

Experimental

Stock solution of DL-methionine (Sisco-Chem) was prepared in double-distilled water. The stock solution of cerium(IV) was prepared by dissolving ceric ammonium sulfate (Trizma Chemicals Co.) in double-distilled water in presence of 0.50 mol dm⁻³ sulfuric acid, and standardized⁵. Cerium(III) solution was prepared by dissolving cerium(III) acetate (B.D.H.) in water and its concentration was ascertained by standard procedure.

All other chemicals were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. NaOH and NaClO₄ were used to provide the required alkalinity and to maintain the ionic strength, respectively.

Kinetic runs :

Kinetic measurements were performed under pseudo-first order conditions with [DL-methionine] in at least ten-fold excess over [Ce^{IV}] at a constant ionic strength of 0.30 mol dm⁻³. The reaction was initiated by mixing previously thermostated solutions of Ce^{IV} and DL-methionine which also contained the necessary quantities of HClO₄ and NaClO₄ to maintain the required acidity and ionic strength, respectively. The temperature was maintained uniformly at 31 ± 0.1°. The course of the reaction was followed by monitoring the decrease in the absorbance of Ce^{IV} in a 1 cm quartz cell of a Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer, at its λ_{max} of 360 nm as a function of time, a wavelength where there was negligible interference from other reagents. Beer's law to cerium(IV) at 360 nm was verified, giving $\epsilon = 3100 \pm 150 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were evaluated from the plots of log [Ce^{IV}] vs time. The first order plots in almost all cases were linear upto 75% completion of the reaction and the k_{obs} values were reproducible to within ±5%.

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